

SOME FEATURES OF MODERN PHILOSOPHY

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights some features of the development of modern philosophy. The paper traces some generalization of the results of the dynamics of philosophical ideas of the second half of the twentieth century and the beginning of the new century. In parallel with this, promising scientific areas of modernity were analyzed. All analyzes were performed on the basis of new scientific discoveries reflecting the philosophical aspects of the world around us.

(INTRODUCTION). In the last century, the dynamics of philosophical ideas were very intense. In the second half of the twentieth century, philosophical currents Positivism (representatives O. Comte, D. Mill, G. Spencer), Empirio-criticism (E. Mach, A. Poincare, R. Avenarius), Existentialism (G.Marcel, K.Jaspers, M.Heidegger, J.Sartre, A.Camus), Phenomenology (E. Husserl), Pragmatism (Ch. Pierce, C. James, J. Dewey) and Psychoanalysis (Z. Freud, K. Hume) have undergone some transformation. The predominance of the ideas of neopositivism (R. Carnap, G. Reichenbach, L. Wittgenstein), postpositivism (K. Popper, T.Kuhn, P. Feyrabend), structuralism (K.Lev-Strauss, J.Lacan, M. Foucault), personalism (E. Mounier, B.Bone, R. Flusillin), neo-Freudianism (E.Fromm) and other philosophical currents.

If the first group of philosophical trends was formed in the period of modernism, then the second group of philosophical trends was formed in the period of postmodernism. If positivism (every science is a philosophy in itself) limited the role of philosophy within the framework of a "synthetic hardener", then neo-positivism, pushing philosophy aside, relies only on the logical-linguistic basis of thinking.

(<https://www.sites.google.com/site/philosophytips/home/pozitivizm-i-neopozitivizm-obsaa-harakteristika-i-evolucia>).

In the modern world, there is also a continuation of that trend of the second half of the twentieth century. The process of a sharp reduction in the workload on the subject of philosophy is traced on the basis of the predominance of positivistic ideas of the last century. Unfortunately, such a negative attitude towards philosophy is growing every year.

Empirio-criticism is essentially a form or some stage of positivism and logically reflects the ideas of the same positivism (<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>).

In the field of existentialism, there are divisions into many independent currents: existential analysis (L. Binswanger), design analysis (M. Boss, A. Holshey), primary analysis (A. Lantieri) and existential counseling (J. Benzhabent, I. Yalom), personalism (J. Lacroix) (<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>). All of them had a psychological bias and they can be united in the group "existential psychology".

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYA. (Literature analysis and methodology). In the system of structuralism (the ratio of the whole to the particulars – E. Titchener, F. De Saussure, R. Jakobson, M. Foucault) of this period, the predominance of the basis of objectivism (objectivity of reality based on maximum consideration of existing facts) and holism (the quality of the ratio of the whole and the particular) is manifested (<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>). In this direction, structuralism somehow completely denies reductionism (simplification of the complex in parts). As a result, structuralism, moving away from philosophy, turns into a promising system in linguistics. Neo-Freudianism (the social determinism of the human psyche – E. Fromm, G. Sullivan, K. Horney) of the second half of the twentieth century differs more in the sociologization of the foundations of Freudianism - the transition from the idea of "the influence of instincts" to "the influence of sociological factors" on the human psyche (<https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>) If we carefully read the texts of many artists, writers, composers of avant-garde modernists, we will practically not find among them pure materialists or positivists. Almost all of them were looking for some other, not material realities, and their activities were often understood as a sacred action. The figures of the images of Kandinsky, Malevich, Chagall are textbook in this regard. However, one can name many other names of avant-gardists, modernists, postmodernists who, some seriously, some in a playful way, and some just outside consciously, saw sacred elements in their activities. All this requires modern aesthetics to re-examine its history and the history of artistic culture, including its last stage.

(RESULTS). Modern philosophy is a rapidly developing system with many, different theoretical and practical changes. There are many interesting trends in modern philosophy. All of them are connected with new scientific and methodological approaches in philosophy. Of these, the following can be distinguished:

1. Dark ecology. This is a rethinking of the relationship between "man and nature". Here one can trace the aspirations of studying "ecology without nature", changes in the world and its coexistence with "non-humans".

Some aspects of this problem in modern philosophy have been generalized in the Timothy Morton project system (Dark Ecology: Towards the Logic of Future Coexistence) and this has been thoroughly investigated by Polina Khanova at the Faculty of Philosophy of Lomonosov Moscow State University (**36.2006. Page 14- 21**).

2. Nonlinear synergetics. Nonlinearity is the birth, or rather the annihilation of elementary things in this world (**37. 2004. page 14**). This is the formation of small fluctuations of perfect systems. The synergetics of the concept associated with a certain volume. Synergetics has many shades and gradations. Here alternative elements of evolution itself are manifested (**38. 2010. page 19**). In a sense, the "relationship between consequences" is rejected here. And this in turn leads to the rejection of the fundamental elements of determinism. Not mixing, but the relative compatibility of incompatible things

and phenomena leads to the process of coevolution. This is a vivid manifestation of the processes of synergetics. For example, people of different worldviews develop ideologically in the same way within certain limited general frameworks. And in natural conditions, the unification of different systems of worldviews leads to chaos.

3. Cosmism and technological immortality. The idea of cosmism begins with "Russian cosmism", which was formed at the beginning of the twentieth century. The new basis of cosmism is based on the ideas of posthumanism by Quentin Mailsou and on the ideas of accelereationism by Mackenzie Wark. A characteristic feature of these ideas is techno optimism. In comparison with other periods of development of society, the modern type of life of people in society differs in contingent (the formation of a group of people of the planet and the erasure of the boundaries of the concept of homeland). And according to Quentin Mailes, this is called activity "after finiteness" (a kind of interpretation of the metaphysics of things after existentialism in the form of the question "What? Where? Why?") (39. buro247.ru/culture/expert/23okt-2019.modernfilosofhy.html).

4. Posthuman. The freedom of the idea of posthumanism flows in two directions: in the process of human thinking and the specificity of the human environment. If the first direction traces the slowness of human thought in relation to the information flows of the world that permeates it, then the second direction highlights the multiplicity of human coexistence in different living conditions, as well as the formation of a new type of people with qualitatively new foundations of thinking (fundamentals of thinking: computer science, bionics, semiotics, cybernetics) (40. 2017. Page 17-29)

5. Cyber Gothic. The essence of Gothic philosophy is the revival of the inanimate (the transition from the spiritual to the material or "the relationship of the living and the dead, as well as the bet of life against the line of death"). Some of the foundations of this problem have been studied by M. Fischer, Deleuze, Guattari, Worrygram, F. Mary, N. Wiener, Ursula Le Guin, Arthur Clark. In fact, this is a new attempt to realize the inner possibilities of capitalism and to smooth out the contradiction of international science fiction with "horror" (horror is Lovecraft, the effect of the unknown mythological). Another feature of this idea is the practice of cognitive detachment from reality and a step in the other direction from the transcendent zone (41. 2018. Page 43-62). The idea of cyber-Gothic is a new approach in philosophy. It is based on non-standard interpretations and characteristics of the thinking environment of the formation of the same thinking (the theory of Darko Suvin "science fiction"). Experiments on cyber gothic were conducted at the center "Base" and "Experimental School" named after Rodchenkov at the RSUH.

6. Flat ontology. Traditional questions of ontology: What really exists? They are connected with the foundations of Hegel's theory of the "absolute Idea" and some elements of spiritualism. According to this idea, in the scheme of the structure of the world (top – middle - bottom), only the middle of this vertical (the location of the person) is essential. But the essence of this part of the vertical has become qualitatively different (42.2015. page 43 –51). A deeper analysis of the basics of flat ontology was made in the laboratory of the Moscow Video Game Research Center at Lomonosov Moscow State University.

7. Anti anthropocentrism.

- A new critical approach of anthropocentrism in the form of the movement of speculative reality and criticism from radical materialists forms the basis of the idea of anti-anthropocentrism. The author of this idea is I. Chubareva. It originated at the Institute of Social Sciences and Humanities at Tyumen State University. The following can be traced in this idea: formation of a new approach to reality;
- the presence of a person in this world in addition to the will of the same person (staying in problematic situations, problematic spaces and problematic periods of a person's life);
- study of the theological problem in naturalistic reduction and externalism (practical attitude to human life);
- formation of "thoughts about the unthinkable";
- the development of transcendental humanism and artificial intelligence, the science of neurophysiology, hybrid natural sciences.

8. Unpacking technology. At the University of Irvine (California), under the leadership of Professor Harry Lynch, experiments are being conducted on conducting an unpacking (thinking stimulators) into Synapse channels (channels of movement of thought neurons). This activates brain activity. As a result, a person's thinking and memory improves. At the same time, under the leadership of Dr. Rudolf Linii, work is underway to create microfibrils for transmitting information based on nano technology. With the help of blood vessels, these fibers transmit signals to the visual, auditory and taste points of the brain. They create the necessary images there and a person with his eyes closed begins to see everything, hears everything with his ears closed, and also feels the taste of food without eating. In addition, sitting in his house, a person can virtually travel around the world. If these identical signaling elements are injected into the blood of two people, then they begin to telepathically recognize each other, as well as telepathically communicate with each other. This system of influence on the human brain opens a new direction in philosophy – "Communication with the mind".

9. New regeneration. On the part of biologists Sem Stop and Ellen Herbert Karst (USA), trace elements were created to help cells regenerate. They were created on the basis of nanotechnology. These elements are 1000 times smaller than a simple human hair and they help the body to repair damaged or cut body tissues. In the natural environment, the damaged areas of the body are protected by scar cells. Scars heal wounds, but they don't repair them. These same cells give strength to cells to repair tissue on cut or injured areas of the body. As the cut nails or hair of a person grows again, so will the cut legs, arms or other human organs grow. This is especially useful for preventing diseases of the kidneys, liver and other damaged human organs. In addition, under the leadership of Dr. Gabriel Vargas (USA), living biological sheets (biological weaves) based on nano technology were created. They are created according to the technique of layered liquid. These liquids are indeed a large concentration of cells of the same type (10 - 30 thousand and cells in one layer of the leaf). Based on the BIOS technique and both of them are injected into the human body. They repair damaged internal organs of a person.

10. New Genome reading. It is known that the tissues on the human skin are renewed every 28 days. It was founded by Dr. Herbert Chenemiz USA. But he's using protein HF – KB in the cell introduced a "rejuvenation" drug into the tissue of mice. Where it spread to the

preparations of the body tissue began to rejuvenate. Doctors David Sampler and Christoph Wisfart (USA) also worked on this. First, they identified the "dispatcher's cell" (Sertabin) in mice. Then, based on the elements of the same cell, a rejuvenating drug "reservation" was created. When this was applied to 40 mice, then the growth of life expectancy in experimental animals was traced. Currently, work is underway to create the same drug for humans. Here we can highlight the works of biologists Krik Venter and Kariya Stefanson from Iceland. The development of modern philosophy has many directions, which are reflected in the formation of different worldviews among people. **(40. buro247.ru/culture/expert/23okt-2019.modernfilosofhy.html).**

In this sense, some problems of epistemology of the late XX – early XXI century were highlighted in the studies of V. I. Shinkaruk **(43. 1976. [crp28 -36](#))**, G.L. Glezerman **(44.1978. [Page 9 - 13](#))**, A.I. Yatsenko, N.F. Tarasenko, N.M.Esipchuk, M. L. Zlotina, I. V. Bychko **(45. 1980. [Page 28 - 252](#))**. Questions of the philosophy of the development of society were developed in the works of V. Willebrand **(46. 1997. [Page 41 - 44](#))**, A. Sharipov **(47. 2010. [crp44 - 56](#))**, O.V. Boyko **(48. 2003. [Page 85 - 97](#))** and other scientists. Some issues of computerization and informatization of the humanitarian sphere were studied by Z. Mukhamedova **(49. 2010. [Page 66 - 68](#))**. A characteristic feature of these studies is that they reflect some aspects of computer intelligence and information development. Intuition and related human creative work were analyzed on a modular basis **(50.2004. [page 12 -13](#))**. Intuition and related creative work of a person were analyzed on a modular basis **(51.2002. [Page 13-15](#))**

(DISCUSSION). In this field of science, the following changes can be distinguished:

- New research on the "Drake Equation" ($A = N + P + f_1 + \dots + f_5$) – study of the number of exoplanets relative to stars in the Department of Astronomy at Harvard University;
- Search for elements of life in other planets through the analysis of the composition of gas (works by Sarah Horst. Seattle University);
- Convergence Theory (a new interpretation of the theory of Evolution at the University of Cambridge);
- Project "Minerva B-2207" (research at Harvard University);
- The New behaviorism of Roger Herman (diversity of other intelligences);
- New studies of radio waves from the universe (studies at the Molonglo Observatory-Australia);
- New research on the rhythm of sounds (research at the University of Cambridge);
- Study of traces of technological civilization based on elements of carbon chloride in the composition of the planet's atmosphere.
- Studying the problem of the essence of life and its origin in the new conditions of modernity revealed unresolved issues on autogenesis, ectogenesis, epigenesis. Here we can highlight the following points related to the question of the origin of life:
 - Creationism (life is created by a supernatural being);
 - natural philosophy (life arose as a result of a spontaneous process of origin);
 - panspermia (life is brought from other space objects. F. 's researchCligue, S.Arrhenius, Helmholtz);

- biochemical evolution (theories of W. Harvey, Oparin);
- cell theory (theory of M.Schleiden, T.Schwann);
- synthetic, molecular –dynamic, mathematical, recombinant cellular interpretation of Charles Darwin's theory of evolution.

All these works constitute the applied natural science basis of philosophy, they are part of a large group of issues that characterize the essence of the specifics of the development of modern philosophy. They reflect some elements of the research of V.S. Solovyov, G.Bashlyar, G. Reichenbach, Z. Freud, K. Tsiolkovsky, S. Trubetskoy on the issues of movement, change, development and processes of cognition **(52.1991.page 313 –339,456 -475)**.

(CONCLUSION). here are specific features in the relationship between technological progress and human activity. Here the dependence of a person on technological progress is more and more traced. At first it was dependence on machines and aggregates, then it became dependence on robots and now it is dependence on artificial intelligence. Such dependence is similar to serfdom – a person is simultaneously free and subordinate to the owner. This is the result of the struggle for human life in nature. Partially defeating nature, man loses to technological progress. And this is dangerous. Because the more technological progress, the greater the danger of man-made disasters. Moreover, every year the difference in the lag of a person from technology is greater and greater. By will, not by will, a person has to adapt to the power of technology and artificial intelligence. The most dangerous thing here is socio-psychological technologies. They directly affect a person's life and health. In this, against the will of a person, there is a change in the psychological attitude of life.

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